

What Drives the Tamil Voter?

A Study on Socio-Political Influences on Voting Behaviour

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Abstract

Voting is the cornerstone of any democratic system, providing citizens the right to choose their representatives and influence government policies. It ensures public participation in the political process. In a diverse country like India, voting behavior is influenced by various factors such as socioeconomic background, education, media exposure, caste, religion, and political ideologies. This study explores the multifaceted factors influencing voting behavior among the electorate in Tamil Nadu. The findings reveal that voter turnout remains relatively consistent across different educational backgrounds and gender groups, with the highest participation observed among postgraduates (84.8%) and men (87.1%) compared to women (76.9%). Lack of faith in the candidates emerged as the most cited reason for not voting, with 37.5% of respondents highlighting it. Among all factors influencing voter decisions, party or candidate's past performance (57.8%), pre-election promises (42.2%), candidate's educational qualification (34.5%), and long-standing party loyalty (31.9%) were the most prioritized. Factors like caste, religion, and monetary inducements were notably less influential in determining voter choice. Celebrity influence was not a dominant factor in the current study, with only 10.9% of respondents stating they were influenced by celebrity statements while voting. A significant 59.1% reported not being influenced at all, while 30% showed occasional susceptibility. NOTA (None of the Above) voting behavior varied significantly across demographics. Younger respondents, especially those in the 35–44 age group reported the highest usage of NOTA (30.4%), while individuals above 45 years of age rarely reported choosing NOTA, indicating a generational divide in its acceptance as a voting tool. Urban voters (27.3%) were more likely to use NOTA than their rural counterparts. Gender differences were also evident—more women reported voting for NOTA, yet only 15.4% viewed it as a good option, compared to 31.4% of men.

Keywords: *Voting behaviour, NOTA, Party loyalty, Media influence, Freebies, Celebrity influence, Youth voters.*

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Introduction

Voting is a powerful expression of people's judgment. It can reflect either dissatisfaction or appreciation, as discussed in "*Voting and the Rise of Populism: Spatial Perspectives and Applications Across Europe*" by Eveline S. Van Leeuwen and

Solmaria Halleck Vega. Voting behavior varies not only between countries but also across different divisions within a country. Socioeconomic and political factors significantly influence individual voting decisions. In India, caste remains a major factor affecting voting,

particularly in states like Uttar Pradesh and Bihar. As noted by Celia Gueto Melo in *“Voting Behaviour – Understanding Factors Influencing Voter Choice in India,”* a National Election Study conducted after the 2014 Lok Sabha elections found that caste influenced the voting behavior of 33% of voters. Tamil Nadu, however, presents a different political environment dominated by regional parties. The ruling Dravida Munnetra Kazhagam (DMK) and its breakaway counterpart, the All-India Anna Dravida Munnetra Kazhagam (AIADMK), are the two most influential forces. Though other community-based parties like Pattali Makkal Katchi (PMK), Puthiya Thamizhagam, and Viduthalai Chiruthaigal Katchi exist, they have not been able to surpass the dominance of these Dravidian parties. While these parties do not overtly align themselves with any particular community, they often adopt strategic caste-based policies to attract specific voter groups.

Age is a significant determinant influencing voting decisions. Younger voters prioritize progressive ideas, educational qualifications of candidates, and visionary leadership. They are open to change and experimentation. In contrast, older voters value political stability and often remain loyal to traditional parties. Many senior citizens, being less aware of current political developments, tend to stick with familiar parties. This pattern is evident in the present study, where 100% of respondents aged above 64 reported voting based on habitual party support.

Voting behavior also varies by gender. Women often focus on welfare-oriented policies, such as healthcare schemes (e.g., Dr. Muthulakshmi Reddy Maternity Benefit Scheme) and gender equality programs. They prefer empathetic leaders who connect with the common people. On the other hand, men tend to prioritize economic growth policies, job creation, and prefer leaders who are charismatic, agile, and youthful. In a 2024 UK election study (*“How Britain Voted in the 2024 General Election”* by Adam McDonnell), men and women voted similarly—34% of men and 35% of women supported Labour, while 23% of men and 26% of women voted Conservative. However, in the current Tamil Nadu-based study, more gender

differences were observed in voting behaviour. While the party’s past performance and the educational qualification of candidates have emerged as leading factors influencing voting decisions among male respondents, promises made by political parties have been the primary factor of influence among female respondents. Gender differences are more pronounced when it comes to celebrity influence and voting for NOTA, with 64.3% of men stating they are not influenced by celebrities while voting, compared to only 48.7% of women. However, 43.6% of women reported being sometimes influenced by celebrities, showing moderate susceptibility. Similarly, in choosing NOTA (None of the Above), 25.6% of women reported voting for it, compared to 17.1% of men.

Educational qualification of individuals also impacts an individual’s voting behaviour. Many studies have proved that the higher the education level, the greater the participation in politics. However, the current study presents a different trend—revealing no correlation between education level and voter turnout in Tamil Nadu. Individuals across all educational backgrounds reported equal participation in elections. Globally, studies have established that higher education levels are often linked with left-leaning ideologies. A study on American voters, *“Factors Influencing Voting Decision: A Comprehensive Literature Review”* by Waiphot Kulachai et al concluded that educated individuals are more likely to support progressive parties, giving importance to social justice and policies promoting equality, an effect attributed to greater critical thinking and access to information. Similarly, a study on UK’s 2024 general elections (*“How Britain Voted in the 2024 General Election”* by Adam McDonnell), has highlighted that 42% of university graduates supported the Labour Party, compared to only 31% of less educated voters who leaned towards the Conservatives. Educated youth, in particular, tend to focus on global, national, and local issues over caste or religion. In Tamil Nadu, political parties actively seek to appeal to educated youth by focusing on issues such as the Three Language Policy, ‘One Nation, One Vote,’ and ‘One Nation, One Ration,’ thereby positioning

themselves as guardians of this demographic's aspirations.

Media is another critical factor influencing voting behaviour. According to the Lokniti-CSDS National Election Study (2019), as quoted by Celia Gueto Melo in *"Voting Behaviour – Understanding Factors Influencing Voter Choice in India,"* nearly 39% of Indian voters reported using social media to access political information. Media coverage of political developments, campaign strategies, and candidate profiles can shape voter perceptions. In Tamil Nadu, many political parties operate their own television channels to promote their ideologies and reach voters directly. The current study found that 13.8% of respondents were influenced by media in their voting decisions, indicating a moderate but notable impact.

Income level also plays a vital role in shaping voting decisions. According to the study *"How Britain Voted in the 2024 General Election"* by Adam McDonnell (July 8, 2024), the Labour Party performed well across all income groups, ranging from £20,000 to £70,000 and above. However, a study on the U.S. electorate entitled *"Factors Influencing Voting Decision: A Comprehensive Literature Review"* by Waiphot Kulachai et al. shows that higher-income individuals tend to support conservative or right-leaning parties, driven by preferences for lower taxes, minimal government regulation, and pro-business policies. In contrast, lower-income groups often align with left-leaning ideologies that focus on economic equality and welfare policies. The current study corroborates this trend—37.5% of business owners, typically in higher-income brackets, stated that their voting decisions were influenced by economic growth strategies, tax reductions, and subsidies in trading and business offered by political parties. Lower- and middle-income voters, however, prioritize policies aimed at inclusive development and public welfare programs.

Beyond socioeconomic factors, political variables such as party ideology, candidate performance, educational qualifications, and family background of the candidates also significantly shape voter preferences. These social and political dimensions often intersect,

collectively influencing the voting behaviour of individuals.

Another crucial aspect of modern elections is the NOTA (None of the Above) option, which was introduced in the 2014 Lok Sabha elections in Tamil Nadu following a 2013 Supreme Court ruling. NOTA allows voters to formally reject all candidates without abstaining from voting, serving as a tool to encourage greater participation and provide a legitimate form of protest. The current study revealed that 37.5% of respondents abstained from voting due to a lack of faith in the candidates. NOTA was introduced to provide an option for voters who were dissatisfied with the available choices but still wanted to participate in the electoral process. The study found that 25.5% of respondents see NOTA as a valid option, while the same percentage considers it a waste of vote. Unless NOTA is granted electoral significance, it may remain largely ineffective. Additionally, the study revealed that the use of NOTA varies across different age groups. Older and middle-aged respondents seldom voted for NOTA, while a significant percentage of younger voters have chosen NOTA in past elections.

Table 1. The Performance of NOTA in Tamil Nadu

Year of election	NOTA %
2014 Lok Sabha	1.4%
2016 Assembly	1.3%
2019 Lok Sabha	1.29%
2021 Assembly	0.75%
2024 Lok Sabha	1.07%

Source: TNPSC Thervupettagam, www.tnpscthervupettagam.com, dated 9 June, 2024.

The study aims to examine in detail all the factors that impact the voting behavior of a Tamil voter and how these factors differ across demographics.

Objectives of the Study

The study aims:

- To analyze the impact of socioeconomic factors on voting behavior in Tamil Nadu.

- To explore the major, moderate, and least influential factors affecting voting behavior in Tamil Nadu.
- To analyze gender-wise and age-wise differences in the selection of NOTA (None of the Above) and to understand voters' opinions about NOTA
- To examine the influence of money, freebies, celebrity endorsements, and caste- and religion-based politics on Tamil voters' decisions.

Methodology

The present study investigates the various factors influencing voting behavior among the electorate in Tamil Nadu. A total of 250 respondents participated in the study. Primary data was collected using a structured questionnaire created in Google Forms and distributed both in English and Tamil to ensure inclusivity. For uneducated respondents, the questions were asked orally in Tamil, and their responses were filled in and submitted by the researcher. The snowball sampling technique was employed to collect data. A simple percentage analysis was used to analyze the collected data. In addition, Chi-square tests were applied to examine associations between demographic variables (such as age, gender, educational qualification, and occupation) and responses to specific voting behavior indicators.

Results

Voter Participation by Education Level

The data reveals that individuals across all educational backgrounds have actively participated in the previous election. Among the respondents, 83.3% of those with no formal education, 78.9% with high school education, 84.0% with a bachelor's degree, and 84.8% with a master's degree reported voting. This consistently high voting percentage across different education levels indicates that educational qualification does not significantly influence voter turnout. This conclusion is supported by the chi-square test.

chi-square value =1.851

critical value at the 0.05 significance level =9.488

1.851<9.488

The calculated chi-square value (1.851) is less than the critical value at the 0.05 significance level (9.488). Therefore, it is concluded that there is no significant relationship between educational qualification and voter turnout.

Table 2. Voter Participation by Education Level

<i>Educational qualification</i>	No	Yes
Bachelors	16	84
High school	21.1	78.9
Masters	15.2	84.8
No formal education	16.7	83.3

Figure 1. Voter Participation by Education Level

Voting Participation by Gender

Table 3. Voting Participation by Gender

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Did you vote in the last election?</i>	Percentage
Female	No	23.1
	Yes	76.9
Male	No	12.9
	Yes	87.1

Figure 2. Voting Participation by Gender

Reasons for not Voting in the Last Election

Among the respondents who did not vote, 37.5% cited a lack of faith in the candidates or political parties as the primary reason. Additionally, 35% of non-voters mentioned that they were unavailable on the election day, while 25% expressed a general lack of interest in voting.

Table 4. Reasons for Not Voting in the Last Election

Reasons for Not Voting in the Last Election	Percentage
No faith in candidates/parties	37.5
NO VOTER ID	2.5
Not available on voting day	35
Not interested	25

Figure 3. Reasons for Not Voting in the Last Election

Table 5. Reasons for not Voting Across Different Age Groups

2. Age	No faith in candidates/parties	NO VOTE R ID	Not available on voting day	Not interested
18-24	26.3	5.3	31.6	36.8
25-34	50.0		37.5	12.5
35-44	40.0		40.0	20
45-54	66.7		33.3	0
55-64	0.0		0	0
Above 64	0.0		0	0

Figure 4. Reasons for not Voting across Different Age Groups

The data reveals that non-voting behavior is predominantly concentrated among younger and middle-aged groups, while individuals aged 55 and above showed full participation in the previous election. Specifically, 36.8% of non-voting respondents in the 18–24 age group stated they were not interested in voting, and 26.3% reported a lack of faith in candidates or parties. In the 25–34 and 35–44 age groups, the main reasons were lack of faith (50.0% and 40.0%, respectively) and unavailability on voting

day (37.5% and 40.0%, respectively). The youngest voters (18–24) had the highest percentage expressing disinterest (36.8%), which highlights a concerning trend of political disengagement among youth.

Influence of Celebrities on Voting Decisions

Table 6. Influence of Celebrities on Voting Decisions

Do celebrities influence your voting decision?	Percentage
No	59.1
Sometimes	30
Yes, always	10.9

Figure 5. Influence of Celebrities on Voting Decisions

Only 10.9% of respondents reported that they are always influenced by celebrities in their voting decisions, while 30% said they are influenced sometimes. A majority—59.1%—stated that celebrities do not influence their voting behavior at all. Despite this, the use of celebrities in political campaigns remains widespread in Tamil Nadu. From comedy actors to character artists, many well-known faces are involved in canvassing for major parties. The data here suggests that celebrity appeal does not guarantee electoral influence or success.

Variation in Celebrity Influence by Age Group

Across all age groups, a majority of respondents reported that they are not influenced by celebrities while voting. Among the middle-aged group (35–44), 17.4% stated they are always influenced by celebrities while an additional 43.5% said they are influenced sometimes. Interestingly, only 39.1% in this group said they are not influenced at all, making them the most celebrity-responsive group overall. 15.8% in the 25–34 age group and 7.4% in the 18–24 group said they are always influenced, while 21.1% and 27.8% respectively said they are sometimes influenced. Older age groups showed the least influence. In the 45–54 age group, only 10% reported being influenced by celebrities while voting, whereas among respondents aged 55 and above, there was no reported influence at all.

Table 7. Variation in Celebrity Influence by Age Group

Age	No	Sometimes	Yes, always
18-24	64.8	27.8	7.4
25-34	63.2	21.1	15.8
35-44	39.1	43.5	17.4
45-54	60	30	10
55-64	66.7	33.3	0
Above 64	100	0	0

Figure 6. Variation in Celebrity Influence by Age Group

Variation in Celebrity Influence by Gender

12.9% of male respondents reported that they are always influenced by celebrities while voting, compared to only 7.7% of female respondents. A significant 43.6% of women said they are sometimes influenced by celebrities, indicating a moderate susceptibility. 64.3% of male respondents stated that they are not influenced by celebrities at all and 48.7% of female respondents have stated the same. Overall, a majority in both genders tend to make independent voting decisions, unaffected by celebrity campaigns.

Table 8. Variation in celebrity influence by gender

Gender	No	Sometimes	Yes, always
Female	48.7	43.6	7.7
Male	64.3	22.9	12.9

Figure 7. Variation in celebrity influence by gender

NOTA Selection by Age Group

The data clearly indicates that the 'None of the Above' (NOTA) option has been predominantly chosen by younger voters. Among respondents aged 35–44, 30.4% reported having voted for NOTA, followed by 26.3% in the 25–34 age group and 20.4% in the 18–24 group. In contrast, none of the respondents belonging to

the 45–54, 55–64, and above 64 age groups—have ever voted for NOTA. The fact that older voters have not opted for NOTA may reflect stronger party loyalty, greater satisfaction with the available candidates, or a belief that voting for NOTA is a waste of their vote. Many older voters prioritize political and economic stability. This preference for stability could be a key reason why they refrain from choosing NOTA. This trend is visible in age-wise opinion about NOTA.

Table 9. NOTA Selection by Age Group

Age	No	Not aware	Yes
18-24	74.1	5.6	20.4
25-34	73.7	0	26.3
35-44	69.6	0	30.4
45-54	100	0	0
55-64	100	0	0
Above 64	100	0	0

Figure 8. NOTA Selection by Age Group

Age Wise Perception of NOTA

All respondents aged above 64 (100%) expressed the opinion that NOTA does not provide a clear result, reinforcing the earlier observation that older voters associate it with political instability. Similarly, all respondents in the 55–64 age group viewed NOTA as a waste of a vote, further indicating their reluctance to support an option that does not contribute to the formation of a government. A notable 52.6% in the age group of 25–34 believe that NOTA is a good option to voice dissatisfaction with the candidates or political parties. Among the 18–24 age group,

27.8% supported NOTA as a good choice, while 24.1% felt it does not provide a clear result. Among middle-aged respondents (35–44) 21.7% said NOTA is a good option, an equal percentage (21.7%) viewed it as a waste of a vote. Additionally, 26.1% believed it doesn't help in choosing a candidate. Overall, the data suggests

that younger voters are more likely to see NOTA as a meaningful form of protest while older voters largely reject it as they are more concerned with electoral clarity and political stability. The chi-square result statistically confirms this difference in perception.

Table 10. Age Wise Perception of NOTA

2. Age	I am not aware of it	It doesn't help in choosing a candidate	It doesn't provide a clear result	It is a good option	It is waste of a vote
18-24	11.1	14.8	24.1	27.8	20.4
25-34	0.0	5.3	10.5	52.6	31.6
35-44	21.7	26.1	13.0	17.4	21.7
45-54	10.0	30.0	30.0	0.0	30.0
55-64	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0
Above 64	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	0.0

Figure 9. Age Wise Perception of NOTA

Chi Square Test

Total Chi-Square Value: 29.22986

Critical χ^2 value = 26.296

The calculated chi-square value (29.229) exceeds the critical value (26.296) at a 0.05 significance level, indicating that age and perception of NOTA are not independent of each other.

NOTA Selection by Gender

Among female respondents, 25.6% have reported voting for NOTA, while only 17.1% of male respondents have said they had voted for

NOTA. Women demonstrate a higher preference for NOTA compared to men, as they view it as a democratic tool to express dissatisfaction when political parties fail to deliver on their promises or when elected representatives underperform during their tenure.

Table 11. Gender Wise Perception of NOTA

Gender	No	Yes
Female	74.4	25.6
Male	78.6	17.1

Figure 10. Gender Wise Perception of NOTA

31.4% of male respondents consider NOTA a good option, compared to only 15.4% of female respondents. Conversely, 30% of male respondents also perceive NOTA as a waste of vote, reflecting polarized opinions among men. Among women, only 17.9% share the view that

NOTA is a waste of vote. A larger proportion of women (28.2%) also believe that NOTA doesn't help in choosing a candidate. The survey reveals a significant association between gender and perception of NOTA, as confirmed by the Chi-square test result ($\chi^2 = 11.74 > \text{critical value } 9.49$ at 0.05 significance level).

Chi-Square Value: 11.74209

The critical value of the chi-square distribution at $df = 4$ and $\alpha = 0.05$ (95% confidence level) is 9.49

$11.74 > 9.49$

There is an association between gender and perception of NOTA.

Males are more likely to have a strong opinion on NOTA (either good or wasteful), while females are more likely to lack awareness or see it as unhelpful in decision-making.

Table 12. Gender Wise Perception of NOTA

Gender	I am not aware of it	It doesn't help in choosing a candidate	It doesn't provide a clear result	It is a good option	It is waste of a vote
Female	17.9	28.2	20.5	15.4	17.9
Male	7.1	10.0	20.0	31.4	30.0

Figure 11. Gender Wise Perception of NOTA

NOTA Choice by Place of Residence

27.3% of urban respondents have voted for NOTA—the highest among all groups. This may be due to higher political awareness, greater

exposure to alternate political narratives, or a desire to break away from traditional party loyalties. In semi-urban areas, 18.5% of respondents have chosen NOTA, and 7.4% are not aware of it. In rural areas, 18% have voted

for NOTA, but only 2% reported being unaware of it. This indicates that while rural areas may have party loyalties, there is still some willingness to use NOTA—possibly driven by younger or first-time voters, such as students.

Table 13. NOTA Choice by Place of Residence

Place of Residence	No	Not aware	Yes
Rural	80	2	18
Semi Urban	74.1	7.4	18.5
Urban	72.7		27.3

Figure 12. NOTA Choice by Place of Residence

Table 14. Factors Influencing Voting Behaviour

What factors do you consider while voting	Yes	No	Sometimes
Usual support for a party	31.9	29.3	12.9
Religion	5.2	48.3	12.9
Caste	6	50	9.5
Free Schemes	16.4	26.7	22.4
Media Influence	13.8	29.3	22.4
Education of the candidate	34.5	22.4	17.2
Promises made before each election	42.2	11.2	19
What my friends or family say	11.2	31.9	22.4
Party or candidates past performance	57.8	8.6	12.1
Which party gives more money	6	43.1	16.4

Figure 13. Factors Influencing Voting Behaviour

A majority (57.8%) of the respondents cited that a party or candidate's past performance is the most important factor that influences their voting decisions. The second most important factor is the promises made during election campaigns, cited by 42.2% of respondents, while 34.5% of the respondents have stated that the education qualification of the candidate is the criteria which they prioritize while voting. Party loyalty is still relevant, with 31.9% stating they vote based on usual support for a particular party. Factors like religion, the candidate's caste and cash for vote appear to be the less influential factors among the respondents with only 5.2%, 6%, and 6% respectively citing these factors as the reasons for their voting behaviour. Free schemes (16.4%) and media influence (13.8%) are moderately influential, while family and peer influence play a limited role, with only 11.2% reporting that their decision is shaped by the opinions of friends or family.

Highly Influential Factors

Party or candidate's past performance has been cited as the most influential factor in voting behaviour across most age and gender categories. 83.3% of male voters aged 45–54 consider this as a primary criterion while voting. Among younger voters (18–24 age group), this trend is also evident, with 50% of women and 55.6% of men stating that past performance influences their voting decisions. In the 25–34 age group, 58.8% of men have stated that they consider party or candidate performance while voting. However, among women in the same age group, opinions were split—33.4% considered performance as important, while 33.3% did not. Among the 35–44 age group, a similar trend is observed across genders, with 75% of women and 72.7% of men saying they vote based on past performance. In the 45–54 age group, 83.3% of men cited past performance as influential, while only 20% of women in the category consider this as an important criterion.

Table 15. Party or Candidate's Past Performance

Gender	Age	Party or candidate's past performance (No)	Party or candidate's past performance (Sometimes)	Party or candidate's past performance (Yes)
Female	18-24	5.0	20.0	50.0
	25-34	33.3	0.0	33.4
	35-44	0.0	25.0	75.0
	45-54	40.0	40.0	20.0
	55-64	50.0	0.0	50.0
Male	18-24	11.1	8.3	55.6
	25-34	0.0	0.0	58.8
	35-44	9.1	0.0	72.7
	45-54	0.0	0.0	83.3

Table 16. Promises Made before Election

Gender	Age	Promises made before election (No)	Promises made before election (Sometimes)	Promises made before election (Yes)
Female	18-24	30.0	20.0	50.0
	25-34	70.0	25.0	0.0
	35-44	16.6	16.7	66.7
	45-54	20.0	60.0	20.0
	55-64	50.0	0.0	50.0
Male	18-24	38.9	22.2	38.9
	25-34	68.9	5.9	35.3

	35-44	54.5	18.2	27.3
	45-54	16.7	33.3	50.0
	55-64	0.0	0.0	100.0

Promises made before elections have emerged as the second most influential factor in voting behaviour. In the 55–64 age group, all male respondents (100%) considered election promises as a primary factor influencing their vote, while 50% of women in the same group shared this view. Among younger voters aged 18–24, 50% of women and 38.9% of men have reported that promises made during campaigns

influenced their choices. In the 25–34 age group, a similar trend was observed across both genders, with 70% of women and 68.9% of men stating that election promises did not influence their vote. However, in the 35–44 age group, 66.7% of women considered promises as an influential factor compared to just 27.3% of men stating the same.

Table 17. Candidate's Educational Qualification

Gender	Age	Candidate's education (No)	Candidate's education (No Answer)	Candidate's education (Sometimes)	Candidate's education (Yes)
Female	18-24	40.0	16.0	12.0	32.0
	25-34	66.7	33.3	0.0	0.0
	35-44	16.7	8.3	50.0	25.0
	45-54	60.0	0.0	40.0	0.0
	55-64	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Male	18-24	20.0	22.5	10.0	47.5
	25-34	5.3	47.4	5.3	42.1
	35-44	15.4	38.5	7.7	38.5
	45-54	14.3	0.0	28.6	57.1
	55-64	50.0	0.0	50.0	0.0

Candidate's education has emerged as the third most influential factor in voting behaviour, with 34.5% of overall respondents considering it while voting. Among female voters, education of the candidate is generally not viewed as an important criterion across age groups. In the 25–34 and 55–64 age categories, none of the female respondents considered it influential. Even among younger female voters (18–24), only 32% cited it as important, while 40% did not consider it. In contrast, male respondents give importance to candidate's education while voting. In the 18–

24 age group, 47.5% of males considered it influential compared to only 32% of females. Similarly, 42.1% of men in the 25–34 category and 57.1% in the 45–54 group have stated that the candidate's educational background influences their vote. Female voters tend to prioritize a candidate's experience and past performance over formal educational qualifications, whereas male voters are more likely to view educational attainment as a key indicator of capability and leadership.

Table 18. Party Loyalty

Age	Usual support for a party (Yes)	Usual support for a party (No)	Usual support for a party (Sometimes)
18-24	22.8	36.8	19.3
25-34	36.8	5.3	0.0
35-44	30.4	30.4	17.4
45-54	54.5	36.4	0.0

55-64	33.3	16.7	50.0
Above 65	100		

100% of respondents above 64 years reported that they consistently support the same party while voting, showing the highest level of party loyalty among all age groups. 54.5% of voters aged 45–54 also displayed strong party loyalty. Contrarily, only 22.8% of 18–24 age group category said they vote for the same party consistently, suggesting that younger voters are more experimental while voting. The 25–34 and 35–44 age groups show moderate party loyalty, with 36.8% and 30.4% of respondents, respectively, reporting usual support for the same party while voting. Older voters tend to value stability. Their attachment to senior party leaders and firsthand experience of the leaders' contributions may influence their continued support for the same party. Most older voters tend to vote based on habitual party loyalty

rather than informed choices, as they often lack awareness about recent political developments, candidate profiles, or evolving policy issues. In contrast, younger voters are generally less inclined toward party loyalty. They often seek change, embrace new ideas, and are more inclined toward progressive ideologies such as social and economic justice, sometimes reflecting a more left-leaning outlook.

Moderately Influencing Factors

Free schemes announced by parties during political campaigns, media influence, and family or peer influence are moderately influential factors in voting behavior, with 16.4%, 13.8%, and 11.2% of respondents, respectively, citing them as reasons for their voting decisions.

Table 19. Freebies

Gender	Age	Free schemes offered by the party (No)	Free schemes offered by the party (Sometimes)	Free schemes offered by the party (Yes)
Female	18-24	35.0	35.0	30.0
	25-34	100.0	0.0	0.0
	35-44	33.3	33.3	33.3
	45-54	50.0	50.0	0.0
	55-64	50.0	50.0	0.0
Male	18-24	66.7	19.4	13.9
	25-34	94.1	5.9	0.0
	35-44	100.0	0.0	0.0
	45-54	50.0	0.0	50.0
	55-64	100.0	0.0	0.0
	Above 64	0.0	50	50

In the 18–24 age group, 30% of female respondents considered free schemes as important while making voting decisions, while only 13.9% of males said the same. Among the 25–34 age group, 100% of female respondents and 94.1% of male respondents did not consider free schemes influential. In the 35–44 age group, 33.3% of women considered this factor affecting their voting decisions, while 50% of male respondents in this group stated it was an important voting criterion. In the 45–54 and 55–64 age groups, none of the female respondents

reported being influenced by free schemes, while 50% of male respondents in both groups said it influenced their vote. In the above 64 age group, 50% of male respondents have cited free schemes as a significant factor. Among male voters, free schemes have been an influential criterion primarily for middle-aged (45–54) and older (above 64) respondents, whereas among female voters, this factor has been influential among the younger (18–24) and middle-aged (35–44) groups.

Table 20. Media Influence

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Age</i>	Media influence (No)	Media influence (Sometimes)	Media influence (Yes)
Female	18-24	35.0	30.0	10.0
	25-34	50.0	0.0	0.0
	35-44	25.0	33.3	33.3
Male	18-24	38.9	16.7	13.9
	25-34	11.8	5.9	5.9
	35-44	18.2	27.3	0.0
	45-54	0.0	50.0	33.3
	55-64	100.0	0.0	0.0
	Above 64	0.0	23	77

Media has emerged as a moderately influential factor among male respondents, particularly in the older (above 64) and middle-aged (45–54) categories, with 77% and 33.3% respectively stating it as an influence. Surprisingly media appears to have less impact on younger voters across both genders. Although younger age groups are highly active on social media platforms like Twitter and Instagram, only 10% of female voters and 13.9% of male voters in the

18–24 age group have considered media as an influential factor in their voting decisions. Among female respondents, only those in the 35–44 age group have reported media as an influential factor in their voting decisions, with 33.3% acknowledging its role. While younger individuals may consume more media, it is the older and middle-aged voters who are more influenced by it in their electoral choices.

Table 21. Family or Peer Influence

<i>Gender</i>	<i>2. Age</i>	What my family or friends say (No)	What my family or friends say (Sometimes)	What my family or friends say (Yes)
Female	18-24	50.0	30.0	20.0
	25-34	50.0	0.0	50.0
	35-44	33.3	50.0	16.7
	45-54	60.0	40.0	0.0
	55-64	100.0	0.0	0.0
Male	18-24	77.8	16.7	5.6
	25-34	88.2	5.9	5.9
	35-44	72.7	27.3	0.0
	45-54	33.3	33.3	33.3
	55-64	100.0	0.0	0.0
	Above 64	0.0	66.7	33.3

Among female voters, peer and family influence in voting is comparatively higher than among males. About 20% of women aged 18–24 and 50% of those aged 25–34 stated that they vote based on what family or friends suggest. Overall, 16.7% of female respondents have cited family or peer influence as a significant factor in their voting decisions. However, this influence declines sharply with age, as older female age groups did not consider it influential. Among

male respondents, the influence of family and peers is even less significant. Only 5.6% of men aged 18–24 and 5.9% of those aged 25–34 acknowledged being influenced by these social factors. The influence drops to 0% among men aged 35–44 and 55–64. Interestingly, 33.3% of men aged 45–54 and above 64 reported that family or peer suggestions influenced their voting choices.

Table 22. Money for Vote

Gender	Which party gives more money(No)	Which party gives more money(No answer)	Which party gives more money (Sometimes)	Which party gives more money(Yes)
Female	51.2	17.1	24.4	7.3
Male	38.9	43.1	12.5	5.6

A majority of female respondents (51.2%) said they do not consider which party gives more money when voting, while 7.3% admitted that they do vote based on monetary offers. Additionally, 24.4% of women said they sometimes consider this factor, suggesting a moderate level of influence. Among male respondents, a lower percentage (38.9%) firmly rejected the influence of money. 43.1% chose

not to answer, indicating hesitation in revealing their stance. 5.6% of male respondents have admitted that they vote based on which party gives more money, and 12.5% said they sometimes consider this factor. It can thus be concluded that women are comparatively less influenced by monetary offers from political parties than men.

Table 23. Religion Impact

Gender	Age	Religion of the candidate (No)	Religion of the candidate (Sometimes)	Religion of the candidate (Yes)
Female	18-24	55	10.0	15
	25-34	50	0.0	0
	35-44	50	41.7	0
	45-54	60	40.0	0
	55-64	100	0.0	0
Male	18-24	61.1	2.8	2.8
	25-34	11.8	5.9	5.9
	35-44	27.3	18.2	0.0
	45-54	50.0	33.3	0.0
	55-64	100.0	0.0	0.0
	Above 64	100.0	0.0	0.0

Religion has emerged as one of the least influential factors in voting behaviour, particularly among older respondents of both genders. 100% of voters aged 55–64 in both male and female categories, and 100% of males above 64, reported that they do not consider the religion of the candidate or party while casting their vote. Among female respondents, none in the 25–34, 35–44, 45–54, and 55–64 age groups cited religion as an influential factor. Only 15% of young women aged 18–24 said that religion influenced their voting decision. However, a

noticeable share of middle-aged women in the 35–44 (41.7%) and 45–54 (40%) groups have indicated that they sometimes consider religion while voting. Among male respondents also the influence of religion was minimal. Just 2.8% of men aged 18–24 and 5.9% of those aged 25–34 reported religion as a deciding factor while 33.3% in the 45–54 age group have stated that they sometimes consider it. Overall, it is evident that across all age groups and genders, voters prioritize other factors over religion when making their electoral choices.

Table 24. Caste

5. Community	Caste of the candidate (No)	Caste of the candidate (No Answer)	Caste of the candidate (Sometimes)	Caste of the candidate (Yes)
BC	45.1	33.3	19.6	2.0
General Category	20.0	80.0	0.0	0.0
MBC	68.8	18.8	0.0	12.5
SC	47.8	47.8	0.0	4.3

Caste has emerged as one of the least influential factors in voting behavior, with only 6% of the overall respondents in the study reporting that they consider caste while voting. In Tamil Nadu, political parties often select candidates based on the dominant caste of the constituency, ensuring that most candidates contesting in a particular area belong to its majority community. Furthermore, to secure community-based vote banks, parties frequently make targeted promises aimed at specific caste groups. According to the current study, 12.5% of MBC (Most Backward Class) respondents reported that they consider the caste of the candidate or the alignment of the party with their community as an important voting factor. Among BC (Backward Class) respondents, only 2% admitted to being directly influenced by caste, while a notable 19.6% acknowledged that caste *sometimes* influences their choice, suggesting a moderate level of influence in this group. 68.8% of MBC respondents stated that they *do not* consider caste at all while voting. Among the General Category, only 20% stated that caste plays no role in their decision, while the remaining 80% did not answer, indicating reluctance to disclose caste-based preferences. In the SC (Scheduled Castes) category, 4.3% openly accepted caste influence, while 47.8% stated they have never considered caste while voting.

Conclusion

Assigning greater electoral significance to the NOTA (None of the Above) option can significantly enhance democratic participation in India. For instance, if NOTA receives the highest number of votes in a constituency, a re-election could be mandated, encouraging political parties to field more credible candidates. Such reforms would pressure parties to avoid candidates with criminal backgrounds.

Implementing 33% reservation for women in legislative bodies will likely increase female voter turnout and ensure better representation of women's interests in policy-making.

Adopting term limits similar to the U.S. presidential system, where leaders can only serve two terms, could curb dynastic politics in India. Limiting the Prime Minister and Chief Ministers to two terms would create space for new, capable, and educated leaders to emerge. Additionally, creating direct public conversations or debates between aspiring candidates and citizens, as practiced in the U.S., can help voters make informed choices. These open forums would allow people to judge candidates based on their ideas and vision before elections, thereby reducing the need for options like NOTA, as only deserving, people-approved candidates would contest. Extending elections to a two-day process offers a credible and practical solution to reduce voter absenteeism. Voter willingness for a preferred voting day can be collected in advance. In cases of over-demand for a specific day, priority could be given to vulnerable groups (e.g., elderly, pregnant women, essential workers). This would be especially helpful for migrant workers, daily wage earners, women with domestic responsibilities, persons with disabilities, and the elderly, thereby increasing their participation. International examples from countries like Indonesia and Nigeria show that multi-day voting is a viable and secure practice. Implementing these democratic innovations can make elections more transparent, accountable, and reflective of the people's true will.

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